

***Callimantis antillarum* (Saussure, 1859) in Anguilla**

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Abstract. 1. Observation records of *Callimantis antillarum* from Anguilla are discussed. 2. Complete distribution range of *antillarum* is presented.

In March 2022, Karl Questel, the Project Manager for the Territorial Environment Agency of Saint-Barthélemy, photographed a pair of *antillarum* adults from the island of Anguilla. Upon subsequent correspondence with the current author, Questel reported that the two different individuals, one male and one female, were photographed at the same observation site near The Valley, Anguilla. These observations mark the most easterly known record of this species within the Leeward Islands of the Lesser Antilles and the first known record of any Mantodea for the island of Anguilla.

Discussion. In 1859, Saussure described the male holotype of *antillarum* from the Caribbean island of St. Thomas. Several years later, in 1871, Saussure described the female of this species from museum specimens that had been collected in the Dominican Republic. Since its discovery on St. Thomas over 163 years ago, this species has been found inhabiting several islands throughout the Caribbean and is understood to be precinctive to this region.

Anderson provided a thorough treatment of the biology and taxonomic history of *antillarum* within his 2021 text, *Praying Mantises of the Caribbean*. On page 71 of this work, Anderson provided a distribution range map for *antillarum* that depicted the occurrence of this species on the Caribbean islands of: San Salvador Island of The Bahamas, Hispaniola, Puerto Rico (including Caja de Muertos, Culebra, Mona, Palomino, and Vieques Islands), Turks and Caicos Islands, and St. Thomas within the US Virgin Islands.

Given that there have been just two specimens recorded from Anguilla at the same time and locale, it is possible that this conspecific pair are siblings from an isolated occurrence of an adventive ootheca. It is more likely, however, that an intergenerational population has become established on the island some time ago and has just now become detected. As *antillarum* was

first documented from St. Thomas and has since been recorded from many additional Caribbean islands, we know that inter-island dispersal has taken place at some point in the past— and this process may have involved localized extinction events and recolonizations of various islands.

The origin point of the species is difficult to determine but it is safe to assert that the chronology of collection records has nothing to do with the actual dispersal timeline, i.e. although the Anguilla population is the most recently discovered, it does not mean that this is the most recent colony that has been established. This colony could very well be the most ancient and we are just now discovering it. It is possible that one of the islands within the Lesser Antilles is the original population core of this species and it has since dispersed west to inhabit the much larger islands of the Greater Antilles (perhaps facilitated by human travel/trade within the Caribbean). Likewise, *antillarum* may just as well have recently colonized Anguilla from Puerto Rico/Virgin Islands and is slowly dispersing east. In any case, Questel's observations from Anguilla are significant, in that no other species of Mantodea has been charted from the island to date. It is likely the case that the distribution ranges of many Mantodea species of the Caribbean are much wider than what is currently known and that we are just now documenting these dispersed colonies with more thorough explorations and digital documentation.

Figure Plate 1. Distribution range map of *Callimantis antillarum*: Anguilla, The Bahamas (San Salvador Island), Hispaniola, Puerto Rico (including Caja de Muertos, Culebra, Mona, Palomino, and Vieques Islands), Turks and Caicos Islands, US Virgin Islands (St. Thomas)

	<i>C. antillarum</i>
GREATER ANTILLES	
Cayman Islands	
Cuba	
Dominican Republic	X
Haiti	X
Jamaica	
Puerto Rico	X
LESSER ANTILLES	
LEEWARD ISLANDS	
Anguilla	X
Antigua & Barbuda	
British Virgin Islands	
Guadeloupe	
Montserrat	
Saba	
Saint Barthélemy	
Saint Kitts & Nevis	
Saint Martin	
Sint Eustatius	
Sint Maarten	
United States Virgin Islands	X
WINDWARD ISLANDS	
Barbados	
Dominica	
Grenada	
Martinique	
Saint Lucia	
Saint Vincent & the Granadines	
Trinidad & Tobago	
ABC ISLANDS	
Aruba	
Bonaire	
Curaçao	
LUCAYAN ARCHIPELAGO	
The Bahamas	X
Turks & Caicos Islands	X

Figure Plate 2. Occurrence of *Callimantis antillarum* in the main islands of the Caribbean

01, *Callimantis antillarum* adult male. [Lat: 18.218152, Lon: -63.052465] The Valley, ANGUILLA 11.27.21 (Photo: Karl Questel)

02, *Callimantis antillarum* adult male. [Lat: 18.218152, Lon: -63.052465] The Valley, ANGUILLA 11.27.21 (Photo: Karl Questel)

03, *Callimantis antillarum* adult female. [Lat: 18.218152, Lon: -63.052465] The Valley, ANGUILLA 11.27.21 (Photo: Karl Questel)

04, *Callimantis antillarum* adult female. [Lat: 18.218152, Lon: -63.052465] The Valley, ANGUILLA 11.27.21 (Photo: Karl Questel)

05, *Callimantis antillarum* adult female. [Lat: 18.218152, Lon: -63.052465] The Valley, ANGUILLA 11.27.21 (Photo: Karl Questel)

References.

ANDERSON, K. (2021): *Praying Mantises of the Caribbean*. 1st edition. Las Vegas: Kris Anderson.

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